

Determination of Nutritional Values and Elemental Analysis of Some Fruits from Bago Region

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Abstract

In this research, the fruit samples (Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple) were collected from BagoMyoma Market, Bago Division. Nutritional values and mineral contents present in collected fruit samples were determined. For the nutritional value investigation, moisture content, ash content and protein content were determined. The observed values indicated that the moisture content of all fruit samples were very high. The highest value of moisture content (91.5 %) was found in Watermelon sample. The ash contents of the fruit samples on wet basic were found to be 0.23 %, 0.25 %, 0.63 % and 1.82 % for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of ash content (1.82 %) was found in Pineapple. The protein content of the fruit samples were determined by Lowry's method. The protein contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 0.59 g/100g, 0.39 g/100g, 0.87 g/100g and 0.49 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of protein (0.87 g/100 g) was found in the orange sample. By studying the results obtained from the mineral content determination of the four fruit samples, it was observed that the highest value of Mg (31.21 mg/100 g) was present in Watermelon, that of Ca (34.35 mg/ 100 g) was found in Orange, K (270.10 mg/ 100g) and P (16.4 mg/ 100 g) in Apple and Fe (3.45 mg/ 100 g) in Pineapple. The general order of the mineral composition of the four fruit samples was found as K>Mg>P>Ca>Fe. The research data indicate that the fruit samples are nutritionally rich. The consumption of these fruits may help overcome nutrient deficiencies that are prevalent in poor and rural areas. The current work is to provide the reference data and public awareness regarding the consuming of these fruits as potential healthy foods for this Bago Region.

Keywords: Nutritional values, Mineral contents, Lowry's method

1.Introduction

Fruits are important source of energy and nutrients for human beings with availability only during specific season. People of all age groups like them. Fruits and vegetables are an important component of a healthy diet and, if consumed daily in sufficient amounts, could help prevent major diseases such as cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) and certain cancers. According to The World Health Report 2002, low fruit and vegetable intake is estimated to cause about 31% of ischaemic heart disease and 11% of stroke worldwide. Overall, it is estimated that up to 2.7 million lives could potentially be saved each year if fruit and vegetable consumption was sufficiently increased (Mengel, 1982).

1.1 Traditional Components of Fruits

1.1.1 Water

The most abundant single component of fruits and vegetables is water, which may account for up to 90% of the total mass. The maximum water content varies between individual fruits and vegetables, because of structural differences. Cultivation conditions that influence structural differentiation may also have a marked effect (Barrett, *et al*, 2007).

1.1.2 Organic acid

There are two types of acids, namely aliphatic (straight chain) and aromatic acids. The most abundant acids in fruits and vegetables are citric and malic (both aliphatic) acids.

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However, large amounts of tartaric acid occur in grapes. Malic acid is the major component in oranges and apples. The acid content of fruits and vegetables generally decreases during maturation.

1.1.3 Proteins

Proteins represent less than 1% of the fresh mass of fruit and vegetable tissues. Leguminous seeds are rich in protein, containing 15% to 30%. The proteins of fruits and vegetables are built from amino acids, but other related simple nitrogenous compounds also occur (Hiza and Bente, 2007).

1.2 Fruits and Vegetables as Direct Sources of Minerals

Minerals are normally classified as macro or micronutrients, based on the relative concentration of each nutrient when those concentrations are adequate for normal tissue function. Macronutrients include potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), nitrogen (N), and phosphorus (P), and their concentrations in plant tissues range from 1000 to 15 000 μ g per gram of dry weight. In contrast, the concentrations of micronutrients usually found in plant tissues are 100 to 10,000-fold lower than those of macronutrients. Mineral micronutrients considered essential in human nutrition include manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), cobalt (Co), sodium (Na), chlorine (Cl), iodine (I), fluorine (F), sulfur (S), and selenium (Se). Macronutrients can also be classified into those that maintain their identity as ions within plant tissues (e.g. K^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}), and those that are assimilated into organic compounds (e.g. N and P) (Jodral-Segado *et al.*, 2003).

2. Experimental

2.1 Collection of Samples

The samples: Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple selected for this research were all bought from Bago Myoma Market, Bago Township. Collection of the samples were carried out during February, 2018.

Fig 2.1 The photograph of the fruit samples at Bago Myoma Market

Figure 2.2 The photograph of Watermelon sample

2.2 Sample preparation

The samples were thoroughly washed with tap water. The outer skin of the Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple were scrapped off using a sharp knife. The seeds of the samples were removed; the hard portion in the middle of the pineapple was also removed and discarded. The inner, fresh, tender and edible portion of each sample was retained and later cut into tiny piece and crushed to homogenize using clean blender, the homogenized samples were stored in a labeled air tight container and used immediately for subsequent analysis.

2.3 Determination of nutritional values

2.3.1 Determination of moisture content

The fresh sample (10 g) was placed in a preheated, cooled and weighed crucible and predried in a steam bath for about 1 h. Then it was heated in the oven at 105 °C for 1 h until constant weight was obtained. Then, it was cooled in a desiccator and weighed. Heating, cooling and weighing were repeated until no change in weight of samples was observed. The moisture content of each variety was calculated as loss in weight of the original sample and expressed as percentage moisture content.

2.3.2 Determination of ash content

The sample (10 g) was placed in a pre-weighed crucible. The sample was carefully heated to a temperature of less than 200° C to remove water and prevent the sample from catching fire. The preliminary heating was done till the sample was thoroughly charred. The charred sample was placed in the Muffle Furnace. Incineration was done at 600° C until a gray ash was obtained and this was removed from the furnace. Then the crucible was cooled in a desiccator and weighed. The process of heating, cooling and weighing was repeated until a constant weight was obtained.

2.3.3 Determination of total proteins

Total proteins from the fruit tissues were determined by Lowry's method using Bovine Serum Albumin as a standard (Lowery, *et al* 1951). This method is based on the fact that protein reacts with FolinCiocalteu's reagent to give a coloured complex. The colour so formed is due to the reaction of alkaline copper with protein and reduction of phosphomolybdate by tyrosine and tryptophan residues present in protein.

The sample (0.5g) was extracted with 10 mL of pH=7 phosphate buffer (1.20 g of sodium dihydrogen phosphate and 0.885 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate in 1 L volume distilled water). The homogenate sample was centrifuged at 500 rpm for 15 min. The supernatant was used for estimation of total proteins. An aliquot of 1 mL was diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and this diluted sample 1 mL was taken in a test tube. 5 mL of solution C (mixed 50 ml of solution 'A' with 1 ml of solution 'B'; solution 'A' containing 2 % Na₂CO₃ in 0.1N NaOH; solution 'B' containing 0.5 % copper sulphate (CuSO₄) in 1 % potassium sodium tartarate) was added and incubated at room temperature for 10 min. Finally, 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (10 g sodium tungstate and 2.5 g sodium molybdate was dissolved in 70 mL water. 5 mL 85% phosphoric acid and 10 mL concentrated hydrochloric acid were added to this. The reagent mixture was refluxed for 10 h. Then, 15 g lithium sulfate, 5 ml water and 1 drop bromine was added and refluxed for 15 min. The resulting solution was cooled to room temperature and the volume was made up to 100 mL with water). The absorbance was measured at 742 nm against reagent blank on UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The amount of protein was calculated using a standard graph prepared from bovine serum albumin (200 µg/mL) and the results obtained were expressed in g/100 g (g of protein in 100 g of sample).

2.3.4 Determination of Mineral Contents

The digestion of the samples was carried out by drying in an oven at 600 °C for 4 hours, the ashes and the crucibles were previously decontaminated with a solution of 10% nitric acid at rest for a night and rinsed. Then, 10 mL of 5% nitric acid was added to the sample, and this mixture was heated until complete dissolution of the ash, which was then filtered. After the sample had reached room temperature, the solution was put into a 250 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to mark with deionized water.

2.3.4.1 Determination of Magnesium, Calcium, Potassium and Iron

The determination of magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), potassium (K) iron (Fe), contents present in each ash sample was performed using an atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Calibration curves for each element were plotted using standard mineral diluted with deionized water. All analyses were performed in triplicate; the results were expressed in milligrams per 100 g of sample on a wet basis (mg per 100 g WB).

2.3.4.2 Determination of Phosphorus

Phosphorus content of fruit samples were determined by using the method as described (AOAC, 2010). The ash sample (0.0100 g) was dissolved in 5 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid solution and the volume make up to 1000 mL with distilled water. This sample solution 1 mL was mixed with 2 mL of combined reagent (Stock A, (4.9 N H₂SO₄) 50 mL + Stock B, (Ammonium molybdate solution) 15 mL + Stock C, (Ascorbic acid solution) 30 mL + Stock D, (Antimony-tartrate solution) 5 mL) and the volume was made up to mark with distilled water. The resulting solution was shaken for uniform mixing. The absorbance of each sample was taken using Ultraviolet (UV) spectrophotometer at 826 nm. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate standards of concentrations 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5 mg/mL were used.

Preparation of Combined Reagents

- A. Sulfuric acid solution, 4.9 N:** Concentrated H₂SO₄ (17 mL) was added to 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to mark with distilled water.
- B. Ammonium molybdate solution:** ammonium molybdate ((NH₄)₆ Mo₇O₂₄•4H₂O) 20 g was dissolved in 500 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to mark with distilled water.
- C. Ascorbic acid solution:** Ascorbic acid (C₆H₈O₆) 9 g was dissolved in 500 mL volumetric flask and the volume make up to mark with distilled water.
- D. Antimony potassium tartrate:** Antimony potassium tartrate K(SbO)C₄H₄O₆•½H₂O was dissolved in 1000 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to mark with distilled water.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Determination of Moisture Content

Determination of moisture content is necessary to calculate the content of other food constituents on a uniform basis (i.e., dry weight basis). Moisture content influences the activities of microorganisms during storage. The higher the moisture content, the more susceptible the sample will be to microbial attack. Moisture content of a food sample is the total water component of the food sample.

In the present research, the moisture contents of the fruits were found to be 91.5%, 85.6 %, 86.3 % and 87.3 % for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The

highest moisture content (91.5 %) was found in the Watermelon sample. The moisture content of the four fruit samples were shown in Table 3.1.

3.2 Determination of Ash Content

Ash refers to the inorganic residue remaining after either ignition or complete oxidation of organic matter in a foodstuff. Ash content represents the total mineral content in foods.

The ash contents of the fruit samples on wet basic were found to be 0.23 %, 0.25 %, 0.63 % and 1.82 % for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. By studying the results, the highest ash content was found in the Pineapple sample. The ash content of the four fruit samples were shown in Table 3.1.

3.3 Determination of Protein content

In this research, the protein content of the fruit samples were determined by Lowry's method. The protein contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 0.59 g/100g, 0.39 g/100g, 0.87 g/100g and 0.49 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of protein (0.87 g/100 g) was found in the orange sample.

Table 3.1 Results for the Nutritional Values of the Fruit Samples

Samples	Moisture content (%)	Ash content (%)	Ash content (%)	Protein content (g/100 g)
		Wet basic	Dry basic	
Watermelon	91.5	0.23	2.71	0.59
Apple	85.6	0.25	1.74	0.39
Orange	86.3	0.63	4.60	0.87
Pineapple	87.3	1.82	14.33	0.49

(a) Moisture content of the fruit samples

(b) Ash content (wet basic) of the fruit samples

(c) Ash content (dry basic) of the fruit samples (d) Protein content of the fruit samples

Figure 3.1 Comparison for the Nutritional values of four fruit samples

3.4 Determination of Mineral Contents

Minerals have both direct and indirect effects on human health. The direct effects of minerals focus on the consequences of their consumption on human nutrition, while the indirect effects refer to their incidence in fruit and vegetable quality and subsequent consumer acceptance. From a direct nutrition standpoint, potassium has the biggest presence in both fruits and vegetables, but nitrogen and calcium show major impacts on horticultural crop quality.

In the present work, the mineral contents (Mg, Ca, K, Fe and P) of four fruit samples were determined by using AAS.

The magnesium contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 31.21 mg/100g, 24.12 mg/100g, 21.13 mg/100g and 23.25 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of magnesium (31.21 mg/100 g) was found in the Watermelon.

The calcium contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 6.28 mg/100g, 14.65 mg/100g, 34.35 mg/100g and 18.45 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of calcium (34.35 mg/100 g) was found in Orange.

In this project work, potassium was found as the most abundant mineral than magnesium, calcium and iron. The potassium contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 115.08 mg/100g, 270.10 mg/100g, 136.36 mg/100g and 211.03 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of potassium (270.1 mg/100 g) was found in the Apple.

The iron content was found to be lower than the other minerals for all the four fruit samples. The iron contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 0.52 mg/100g, 0.39 mg/100g, 1.08 mg/100g and 3.45 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The Pineapple sample contains the highest value of iron (3.45

mg/g). The general order of the mineral composition of the four fruit samples was found as $K > Mg > Ca > Fe$. The mineral contents of the four fruit samples were shown in Table 3.2.

The phosphorus content was determined by the method as described in section (1.2.2). The phosphorus contents of the fruits on wet basic were found to be 12.6 mg/100g, 16.4 mg/100g, 14.3 mg/100g and 4.0 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of phosphorus (16.4 mg/100 g) was found in Apple.

Table 3.2 Mineral Content of the Four Fruit Samples

Samples	Mg (mg/100g)	Ca (mg/100g)	K (mg/100g)	Fe (mg/100g)	P (mg/100 g)
Watermelon	31.21	6.28	115.08	0.52	12.6
Apple	24.12	14.65	270.10	0.39	16.4
Orange	21.13	34.35	136.36	1.08	14.3
Pineapple	23.25	18.45	211.03	3.45	4.00

(a) Magnesium content of the fruit samples

(b) Calcium content of the fruit samples

(c) Potassium content of the fruit samples

(d) Iron content of the fruit samples

(e) Phosphorus content of the fruit samples

Figure 3.2 Comparison of the mineral contents present in four fruit samples

4. Conclusion

Moisture content is the total water component of the food sample. It is used to determine the quality of food sample. The moisture contents determined for the fruit samples were found to be 91.5%, 85.6 %, 86.3 % and 87.3 % for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. These values indicate that the moisture content of all four samples were very high. Therefore, consumption of these fruits by humans could serve as a better thirst quencher during hot weather conditions.

The Ash content of a biological material is the inorganic residue that remains after organic matter has been burnt. The ash contents of the fruit samples on wet basic were found to be 0.23 %, 0.25 %, 0.63 % and 1.82 % for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The ash composition is the amount of mineral elements in food. According to the results, the Pineapple fruits contain more mineral than any other three fruits.

Minerals are essential for the maintenance of human health. The average daily reference values of recommended dietary allowances (RDA) for adults established by USA National Institute of Health (NIH) for men and women, from 19 to 70 years, are: 700 , 310-420, 1,000-1,200, 4700, 8-14 mg per day of P, Mg, Ca, K and Fe, respectively.

By studying the results obtained from the mineral content determinations of the four fruit samples, it was observed that the highest value of Mg (31.21 mg/100 g) was present in Watermelon fruit, that of Ca (34.35 mg/ 100 g) was found in Orange, K (270.10 mg/ 100g) and P (16.4 mg/ 100 g) in Apple and Fe (3.45 mg/ 100 g) in Pineapple. The general order of the mineral composition of the four fruit samples was found as K>Mg>P>Ca>Fe.

In this research, the protein content of the fruit samples were determined by Lowry's method. The protein contents of the fruits on wet basis were found to be 0.59 g/100g, 0.39 g/100g, 0.87 g/100g and 0.49 mg/100g for Watermelon, Apple, Orange and Pineapple, respectively. The highest value of protein (0.87 g/100 g) was found in the orange sample.

The research data indicate that the fruit samples are nutritionally rich. The consumption of these fruits may help overcome nutrients deficiencies that are prevalent in poor and rural areas. The current work is to provide the reference data and public awareness regarding the consuming of these fruits as potential healthy foods for this Bago Region.

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